

ENHANCING STUDENTS' ORAL COMMUNICATION SKILLS IN NATIVE LANGUAGE LESSONS

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Abstract. *This article discusses how using exercises and tasks aimed at developing students' oral speech skills in native language lessons plays a crucial role in fostering their thinking, creative, and critical thinking abilities, as well as fostering a person with developed speech culture.*

Keywords: *communication, speech culture, speech competence, oral speech, speaking skills, listening skills.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье рассматривается важность использования упражнений и заданий, направленных на развитие навыков устной речи учащихся на уроках родного языка, в воспитании их мыслительных, творческих и критических способностей, а также личности с развитой культурой речи.*

Ключевые слова: *коммуникация, культура речи, речевая компетенция, устная речь, навыки говорения, навыки аудирования.*

It is known that the main goal of the subject of the native language at the stage of general secondary education is to develop a person with a developed speech culture who can think independently and creatively, freely express his thoughts. Developing students' oral speech in native language lessons is based on communicativeness; the methodologist M. Karakhodjaeva recognizes the importance of developing students' oral speech and expresses the following opinion: "The role of oral speech in daily communication is incomparable." Teaching oral speech involves listening, understanding, and speaking. They are inseparable parts, and they cannot be taught separately. [1; P. 24.] In developing and improving students' oral speech, it is important to develop the listening and speaking skills of speech activity together.

Psychologists recognize that the speech process is expressed in the following three stages: "1. Orientation toward achieving a set goal is the process of thinking and reasoning; 2. Analytical-synthetic process - the process of

forming an opinion; 3. The implementation process - the emergence and expression of speech [2; P. 388]. First of all, speech begins to be formed through thought. At this stage, planning occurs as a result of thinking and reasoning. In the second stage, a thought is expressed in a planned speech process that achieves a specific goal.

Z. Salisheva describes this stage as follows: "It is well known that listening and speaking are closely related phenomena. Verbal communication consists of directly listening to the interlocutor's speech and responding to it while understanding it, and in this process, each of the interlocutors acts as both a listener and a speaker" [3;P.74]. In the third stage, external speech arises due to refined internal speech. Polished internal speech follows the norms of language, and lexical and syntactic units are activated in this process. In the process of expressing one's opinion, telling one's attitude, being aware of information about the subject, the evidence of the expressed opinion with scientific data, paying attention to the communicative qualities of speech during the reflection, thinking and expression of the idea is the main and necessary criterion.

In order to avoid pausing in the process of speaking, not being able to find the necessary words, not being able to connect the thought with the next thought, it is necessary to know how to express in speech clearly, consistently and means of connecting sentences in terms of meaning. This criterion is characterized by vocabulary. Scholar K. Kasymova: "Teachers work weakly to transform words whose meaning, correct pronunciation and spelling, and use in speech are explained into the active vocabulary of students. In order to turn the learned words into an active vocabulary of students, it is necessary to teach the use of these words in oral and written communication, to choose, if necessary, to prepare and conduct exercises aimed at forming the ability to use them correctly" [4; 47], - says.

According to R. Yuldashev, "Speaking primarily involves knowing words and their pronunciation, recalling the necessary word during the presentation of a thought, forming it grammatically, recalling the next word required by the form of the formed word, forming it grammatically, and thereby creating an infinite chain of pronouncing the syntagma that arises in the mind" [5; P. 164.] This process is more manifested in the development of writing skills than in the development of oral speech. The reason for this is that in the process of oral speech, students do not feel the need to pay sufficient attention to diction and intonation when pronouncing words correctly, sentences are not formed

grammatically, many of their sentences are formed quickly, especially in the process of writing the text, a certain time is given for grammatical formation, of course, speaking without mistakes is required.

The ability to think abstractly grows, while the concrete-figurative components of thinking are preserved and developed. Critical thinking activity develops significantly, and its independence and activity increase. The teacher's task is to form and develop the necessary thinking operations for any age of the student, based on logical thinking [6; 90-91 p.]. Specifically, in the current native language textbooks of general secondary schools, there are many exercises and tasks that encourage the development and improvement of students' oral speech, speaking, and thinking skills and abilities, such as "express your attitude," "explain," "talk," "dispute," "express your opinion," "definition," "tell," "recount," "think," "speak," "tell," "explain," and such tasks are important for developing students' skills in mutual communication, free expression of opinion, listening to the interlocutor's speech, logical thinking, and drawing conclusions during the lesson.

The acquisition of speech literacy depends, firstly, on linguistic factors such as the thorough mastery of the modern Uzbek language and its existing means of expression, full adherence to the norms of the literary language, and secondly, on socio-psychological factors such as adherence to certain moral and ethical norms during communication, being attentive to one's speech by respecting one's own and others' opinions, and fully complying with cultural requirements when speaking, listening, conversing, and discussing appropriately and reasonably. Reacting to every situation in a gentle tone, using words in their right place according to their meaning when speaking and writing, enriching speech with necessary and clear, useful words is a means of demonstrating speech culture along with enhancing the spiritual qualities of students. Explaining to the student the insignificance of a useless word in the life of every person through life events and examples, and making it clear that a good word has high value, constitutes the core of the educational process.

The main goal of developing speech competencies is not only to convey students' independent thoughts clearly and understandably to the listener but also to positively influence the worldview and beliefs of those around them. Consequently, in addition to acquiring knowledge through speech, the student expresses and influences their thoughts through speech.

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